

Understanding Typhoid Fever Transmission Dynamics in The Presence of Multiple Interventions– Optimal Control and Cost-Effectiveness Analysis

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Abstract

The consequences of typhoid fever in the host are a significant public health concern. Most nations in Sub-Saharan Africa, Asia, and North America are experiencing their highest rates of typhoid cases and deaths due to inadequate sanitation. This study focuses on a non-autonomous deterministic model that describes the spread of typhoid fever infections in human host communities. The model is built up by taking into account the optimal vaccination of susceptible births and immigrants, the treatment of infectious persons, and proper environmental sanitation. The new optimal control model was analyzed using Pontryagin's maximal principle. The impacts of using various combination tactics incorporating the deployment of at least one of the three control interventions were demonstrated through numerical simulations. The simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of each strategy in reducing disease prevalence. Using the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER), a cost-effectiveness analysis was performed to support the numerical results obtained from the numerical simulations of the optimality system. This aids in determining the most economical approach that can be used in places with limited resources, such as Nigeria. **Keywords:** Infectious individuals; Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio; Environmental sanitation; Typhoid fever, Optimal control; Vaccination.

INTRODUCTION

Africa has a high prevalence of typhoid fever (TF), which remains a significant issue in many parts of the world [Ashraf *et al.* (2024)]. TF is a highly contagious disease that primarily affects children under the age of ten and is caused by the Salmonella Typhi bacterium [Ashraf *et al.* (2024), cleveland clinic (2025)]. It is spread by contaminated food, inadequate sanitation, and unclean water [Hoinsou *et al.* (2024)]. TF symptoms include high fever, chills, headache, loss of appetite, muscular pains, coughing, nausea, vomiting, constipation, diarrhoea, and "rose spots" rash or pale pink patches, usually on the chest or stomach [Alalhareth *et al.* (2023), cleveland clinic (2025)].

TF mainly impacts countries in South and Southeast Asia, Africa, the Caribbean, and Central and South America. Eleven to twenty-one million people globally get TF annually, resulting in 128,000 to 161,000 deaths and a significant cause of morbidity in children between the ages of one and five [cleveland clinic (2025), Hoinsou *et al.* (2024)]. Vaccination is used to prevent TF, while oral antibiotics are used to treat TF [Ruthie *et al.* (2022)].

Numerous mathematical models of TF have been developed to address the disease's complexity and endemic nature [Ashraf *et al.* (2024), Alalhareth *et al.* (2023), Hoinsou *et al.* (2024), Ruthie *et al.* (2022), Anju *et al.* (1999), Alhassan *et al.* (2024), Lawal *et al.* (2024), Sacrifice *et al.* (2025), Ihsan *et al.* (2023), Hamadjam *et al.* (2021), Abdulai *et al.* (2023), Pontryagin (2018)]. Precisely, [Alhassan *et al.* (2024)] developed a deterministic model for TF that includes two essential interventions namely vaccination and good hygiene —and transformed the model into a fractional-order model using the Caputo derivative. The study divides the human population into susceptible, vaccinated, exposed, asymptomatic infected, symptomatic infected, and recovered compartments and monitors the bacterial load in the environment. They emphasized the need for multifaceted control measures encompassing vaccine coverage, sanitation enforcement, and healthcare capacity building to mitigate typhoid in high-risk regions. However, the model did not consider the effect of the booster vaccine since there is no perfect vaccine for typhoid fever.

Similarly, [Abdulai *et al.* (2023)] formulated a mathematical model for the transmission dynamics of TF, taking into account booster vaccination and treatment. It identified equilibrium points and the basic reproduction number. Investigated the local and global stability analysis of the model. The model may exhibit backward bifurcation under certain conditions, suggesting that it may not be enough to eradicate the disease. Sensitivity analysis revealed that transmission rate, recruitment rate, and susceptible fraction are the most influential parameters. Numerical simulations have shown that booster vaccination may not be effective in areas with endemic disease. A significant drawback of their model, nevertheless, was that they neglected to include asymptomatic individuals, a crucial component, in the formulation.

This research extends the work of [Alhassan *et al.* (2024)] to an optimal control problem by introducing control interventions to examine the impact of vaccination, environmental sanitation, and treatment on the symptomatic infectious population, the bacteria in the community, as well as the cost-effectiveness analysis of the optimal control intervention.

METHODOLOGY

According to the recommendations provided by Alhassan *et al.* (2024), the optimal control problem is formulated by considering the three time-dependent control variables $u_1(t)$, $u_2(t)$, and $u_3(t)$. The optimal control problem is solved using the Runge-Kutta fourth-order forward-backwards sweep scheme, implemented in MATLAB. The implementation of the optimality system is carried out under four different control combination strategies, involving the use of at least one of the three time-dependent control functions. These strategies are defined as follows: Strategy 1, S1, is the use of vaccination and treatment only (u_1 , u_2), strategy 2, S2, is the combination of vaccination, and environmental sanitation (u_1 , u_3) only, strategy 3, S3, is the use of treatment and ecological sanitation only (u_2 , u_3), strategy 4, S4, combines all the three control interventions (u_1 , u_2 , u_3).

Formulation of Optimal control model for typhoid fever:

The main objective of this study is to minimize the incidence of symptomatic infectious individuals and the bacterial subpopulation in the community, as well as the costs associated with implementing environmental sanitation, vaccination, and treatment.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dS}{dt} &= \Lambda + \omega V - \left[\frac{(1-u_1(t))\beta(I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C)}{N} + u_2(t) + \mu \right] S \\
\frac{dV}{dt} &= u_2(t) S - \left[\frac{(1-\phi)(1-u_1(t))\beta(I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C)}{N} + \omega + \mu \right] V, \\
\frac{dE}{dt} &= \frac{(1-u_1(t))\beta(I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C)}{N} [S + (1-\phi)V + \rho R] - (\sigma + \mu)E, \\
\frac{dI_a}{dt} &= (1-\tau)\sigma E - (\varpi + \alpha + \mu)I_a, \\
\frac{dI_s}{dt} &= \tau\sigma E + \varpi I_a - \alpha[1 + u_3(t)(1-\theta)] + \delta_1 + \mu I_s, \\
\frac{dR}{dt} &= \alpha I_a + \alpha[1 + u_3(t)(1-\theta)]I_s - \left[\frac{\rho(1-u_1(t))\beta(I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C)}{N} + \mu \right] R, \\
\frac{dC}{dt} &= \gamma_1 I_a + \gamma_2 I_s - (\delta_2 + u_1)C,
\end{aligned}$$

with the associated initial conditions given by

$$S(0) > 0, V(0) \geq 0, E(0) \geq 0, I_a(0) \geq 0, I_s(0) > 0, R(0) \geq 0, C(0) \geq 0.$$

Thus, considering the objective (cost) functional defined as $Z(u_1, u_2, u_3) = \int_0^T \left(A_1 I_s + A_2 C + \frac{1}{2} B_1 u_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} B_2 u_2^2 + \frac{1}{2} B_3 u_3^2 \right) dt$,

where, A_1, A_2 , represent the positive weight constants for the symptomatic infectious and bacterial subpopulations. The optimal control intervention is implemented over the interval $[0, T]$ where the final time interval is denoted by T . The triple control functions characterize the non-linearity of the control intervention. As a result, the nonlinear terms $\frac{1}{2} B_1 u_1^2$, $\frac{1}{2} B_2 u_2^2$, $\frac{1}{2} B_3 u_3^2$ are used to represent the cost associated with the implementation of environmental sanitation (u_1), vaccination (u_2), and treatment (u_3) control strategies.

Therefore, our overall interest is to determine a control pair $u^* = (u_1^*, u_2^*, u_3^*)$ which satisfies

$$Z(u^*) = \min\{Z(u_1, u_2, u_3) : (u_1, u_2, u_3) \in U\},$$

subject to the model dynamics given above, where U is a non-empty Lebesgue's measurable set for the controls $0 \leq u_1(t) \leq 1$, $0 \leq u_2(t) \leq 1$, $0 \leq u_3(t) \leq 1$ with $t \in [0, T]$

The physical meanings of the state variables and parameters of the typhoid fever model are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively, to enhance the understanding of the readers.

Table 1: Description of the variables of typhoid fever model

Variable	Description
S	Susceptible individuals
V	Vaccinated individuals
E	Exposed individuals
I_a	Asymptomatic infectious individuals
I_s	Symptomatic infectious individuals
R	Recovered individual
C	Salmonella typhi bacteria in the environment

Table 2: Description of parameters of the typhoid fever model

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Values (per day)</i>
Λ	<i>Rate at which new members enter the susceptible group</i>	467
ω	<i>Rate of individuals transitioning from V to S</i>	9.041^{-4}
μ	<i>Natural death rate of humans</i>	3.4562^{-4}
Φ	<i>Reduction in transmission due to vaccine efficacy</i>	0.4378
ρ	<i>Reinfection rate for recovered individuals</i>	0.5095
σ	<i>Rate of progression from exposed to infected</i>	0.5000
τ	<i>Fraction progressing to I_a from exposed</i>	0.0931
β	<i>Effective contact rate</i>	0.8883
ν_1	<i>Rate of infectiousness of I_s</i>	0.0019
ν_2	<i>Rate of infectiousness of C</i>	0.0790
α	<i>Mortality rate of symptomatic infected individuals</i>	0.8510
δ_1	<i>Shedding rate of bacteria by people in I_s class</i>	0.0022
δ_2	<i>Reduction rate of bacteria in contaminated environment</i>	0.0645
ϖ	<i>Progression rate from I_a to I_s</i>	0.0020
γ_1	<i>Shedding rate of bacteria by I_a</i>	1
γ_2	<i>Shedding rate of bacteria by I_s</i>	1
θ	<i>Rate of antibiotic resistance</i>	0.0070

Analysis of the optimal control TF model

Here, the formulated optimal control problem is theoretically analyzed using Pontryagin's maximum principle [Pontryagin, (2018)]. By constructing the appropriate Hamiltonian, the optimality system associated with the optimal control problem is derived using the necessary condition.

The Hamiltonian is given as: $H = A_1I_s + A_2C + \frac{1}{2}B_1u_1^2(t) + \frac{1}{2}B_2u_2^2(t) + \frac{1}{2}B_3u_3^2(t) + \lambda_1\{\Lambda + \omega V - [(1 - u_1)\beta(I_a + \nu_1I_s + \nu_2C)/N + u_2 + \mu]S\} + \lambda_2\{u_2S - [(1 - \varphi)(1 - u_1)\beta(I_a + \nu_1I_s + \nu_2C)/N + \omega + \mu]V\} + \lambda_3\{(1 - u_1)\beta(I_a + \nu_1I_s + \nu_2C)/N [S + (1 - \varphi)V + \rho R] - (\sigma + \mu)E\} + \lambda_4\{(1 - \tau)\sigma E - (\varpi + \alpha + \mu)I_a\} + \lambda_5\{\tau\sigma E + \varpi I_a - [\alpha(1 + u_3(t)(1 - \theta)) + \delta_1 + \mu]I_s\} + \lambda_6\{\alpha I_a + \alpha[1 + u_3(t)(1 - \theta)]I_s - [\rho(1 - u_1)\beta(I_a + \nu_1I_s + \nu_2C)/N + \mu]R\} + \lambda_7\{\gamma_1I_a + \gamma_2I_s - (\delta_2 + u_1)C\}$,

where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4, \lambda_5, \lambda_6, \lambda_7$ are the co-state variables.

Theorem:

The optimal controls u_1^*, u_2^*, u_3^* and state variables $S(t), V(t), E(t), I_a(t), I_s(t), R(t), C(t)$ exist. Then there exist adjoint variables $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4, \lambda_5, \lambda_6, \lambda_7$ satisfying:

$$\begin{aligned} d\lambda_1/dt &= -\partial H/\partial S, \quad d\lambda_2/dt = -\partial H/\partial V, \quad d\lambda_3/dt = -\partial H/\partial E, \quad d\lambda_4/dt \\ &= -\partial H/\partial I_a, d\lambda_5/dt = -\partial H/\partial I_s, \quad d\lambda_6/dt = -\partial H/\partial R, d\lambda_7/dt \\ &= -\partial H/\partial C. \end{aligned}$$

$$d\lambda_1/dt = ((\lambda_1 - \lambda_3)(1 - u_1)\beta(I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C))/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_1)(1 - u_1)\beta S(I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C))/N^2 + \lambda_1(u_2 + \mu) - \lambda_2 u_2$$

$$d\lambda_2/dt = -\lambda_1 \omega + ((\lambda_2 - \lambda_3)(1 - \varphi)(1 - u_1)\beta(I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C))/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_2)(1 - \varphi)(1 - u_1)\beta V(I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C))/N^2 + \lambda_2(\omega + \mu)$$

$$d\lambda_3/dt = \lambda_3(\sigma + \mu) - \lambda_4(1 - \tau)\sigma - \lambda_5 \tau \sigma$$

$$d\lambda_4/dt = ((\lambda_1 - \lambda_3)N(1 - u_1)\beta S)/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_1)(1 - u_1)\beta S I_a)/N^2 + ((\lambda_2 - \lambda_3)(1 - u_1)\beta(1 - \varphi) V)/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_2)(1 - u_1)\beta(1 - \varphi) V I_a)/N^2 + ((\lambda_6 - \lambda_3)(1 - u_1)\beta \rho R)/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_6)(1 - u_1)\beta \rho R I_a)/N^2 + \lambda_4(\varpi + \alpha + \mu) - \lambda_5 \varpi - \lambda_6 \alpha - \lambda_7 \gamma_1$$

$$d\lambda_5/dt = -A_1 + ((\lambda_1 - \lambda_3)(1 - u_1)\beta v_1 S)/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_1)(1 - u_1)\beta v_1 S I_s)/N^2 + ((\lambda_2 - \lambda_3)(1 - \varphi)(1 - u_1)\beta v_1 V)/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_2)(1 - \varphi)(1 - u_1)\beta v_1 V I_s)/N^2 + ((\lambda_6 - \lambda_3)(1 - u_1)\beta \rho v_1 R)/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_6)(1 - u_1)\beta \rho v_1 R I_s)/N^2 + \lambda_5[\alpha(1 + u_3(1 - \theta) + \delta_1 + \mu)] - \lambda_6[\alpha(1 + u_3(1 - \theta))] - \lambda_7 \gamma_2$$

$$d\lambda_6/dt = \lambda_6 \mu + ((\lambda_6 - \lambda_3)(1 - u_1)\beta \rho (I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C))/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_6)(1 - u_1)\beta \rho R (I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C))/N^2$$

$$d\lambda_7/dt = -A_2 + ((\lambda_1 - \lambda_3)(1 - u_1)\beta v_2 S)/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_1)(1 - u_1)\beta v_2 S C)/N^2 + ((\lambda_2 - \lambda_3)(1 - \varphi)(1 - u_1)\beta v_2 V)/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_2)(1 - \varphi)(1 - u_1)\beta v_2 V C)/N^2 + ((\lambda_6 - \lambda_3)(1 - u_1)\beta \rho v_2 R)/N + ((\lambda_3 - \lambda_6)(1 - u_1)\beta \rho v_2 R C)/N^2 + \lambda_7(\delta_2 + u_1)$$

The transversality condition given by $\lambda_1(T) = 0$, $\lambda_2(T) = 0$, $\lambda_3(T) = 0$, $\lambda_4(T) = 0$, $\lambda_5(T) = 0$, $\lambda_6(T) = 0$, $\lambda_7(T) = 0$. Since $S(t)$ is free at the final time (t) while $I_s(t)$ occur in the objective functional as a final cost. The **Pontryagin Maximum Principle** gives: $\frac{\partial H}{\partial u_i} = 0$, **The optimal controls** are:

$$u_1^* = \frac{(\lambda_3 - \lambda_1)\beta S(I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C)}{B_1 N} + \frac{(\lambda_3 - \lambda_2)\beta V(1 - \varphi)(I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C)}{B_1 N} + \frac{(\lambda_3 - \lambda_6)\rho \beta R(I_a + v_1 I_s + v_2 C)}{B_1 N}$$

$$u_2^* = \frac{(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)S}{B_2}, \quad u_3^* = \frac{(\lambda_5 - \lambda_6)\alpha(1 - \theta)I_s}{B_3}$$

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the numerical results of the optimal control problem and their discussion in relation to the cost-effective analysis.

Figure 1: Simulation showing the dynamics of the state variables with $u_1, u_2 = s_1$

Figure 2: Simulation showing the dynamics of the states variables with $u_1 u_3 = s_2$

Figure 1 depicts the effect of using Strategy 1 on the transmission dynamics of TF. It is observed that the sizes of symptomatic infectious individuals and the concentration of bacteria in the environment drastically reduce with the implementation of this strategy. To achieve this optimal solution, more effort is required in environmental sanitation compared to vaccination, as shown in the third subfigure

In Figure 2, the effect of using Strategy 2 on the transmission dynamics of TF is demonstrated. It is observed that the number of symptomatic infectious individuals and the concentration of bacteria in the environment quickly diminish from the first 5 days of the implementation of the strategy. This optimal result is achieved with more effort of environmental sanitation is required when using this strategy as the third panel of Figure 2 shows.

Figure 3: Simulation showing the dynamics of the state variables with

The effect of using Strategy 3 on the transmission dynamics of TF is illustrated in Figure 3. It is observed that the number of symptomatic infectious individuals and the concentration of bacteria in the environment with optimal controls are reduced when compared with those without optimal controls. This optimal result is achieved with more effort of treatment than vaccination, as seen in the third panel.

Figure 4: Simulation showing the dynamics of the states variables of model $u_1u_2u_3 = s_4$

Figure 4 illustrates how the implementation of Strategy 4 affects the dynamics of TF in society. It is seen that the number of symptomatic infectious individuals and the concentration of bacteria in the environment with optimal controls diminish from the 5th day of control implementation. This optimal result is achieved through the most effort in environmental sanitation, followed by treatment and then vaccination, as seen in the third panel.

3.1 Cost-effectiveness analysis

We employ the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER). ICER is calculated as

$$ICER = \frac{\text{Change in the costs expended on strategies } p \text{ and } q}{\text{Change in the total number of infection averted by strategies } p \text{ and } q}$$

The rank of the control interventions based on the infection averted with respect to the associated costs follows from the simulation results, and is displayed in Table 3. The ICER as shown in Table 3 is calculated with the aid of the formula above.

Table 3: Increasing order of the total infection averted by the three strategies

Strategy	Total infection averted	Total cost	ICER
$S_3 - u_2(t), u_3(t)$	4.4260×10^5	2.3075×10^6	5.2135
$S_1 - u_1(t), u_2(t)$	5.0755×10^5	3.7895×10^4	-34.9439
$S_2 - u_1(t), u_3(t)$	5.3923×10^5	3.2784×10^4	-
$\mathbb{E}_4 - u_1(t), u_2(t), u_3(t)$	5.3924×10^5	3.2719×10^4	-

It is observed from Table 3 that ICER for S_3 is greater than that of S_1 . On this note, S_3 is excluded from the list of the competing strategies. Therefore, we are led to recalculate the ICER for the two strategies listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Increasing order of the total infection averted by the three strategies

Strategy	Total infection averted	Total cost	ICER
$S_1 - u_1(t), u_2(t)$	5.0755×10^5	3.7895×10^4	0.0747
$S_2 - u_1(t), u_3(t)$	5.3923×10^5	3.2784×10^4	-0.1613
$S_4 - u_1(t), u_2(t), u_3(t)$	5.3924×10^5	3.2719×10^4	-

From the results in Table 4, it is seen that S_1 has an ICER value greater than that of S_2 . Thus, S_1 is excluded from the list of competing strategies. We further re-calculate the ICER for S_2 and S_4 , with the results presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Increasing order of the total infection averted by the three strategies

Strategy	Total infection averted	Total cost	ICER
$S_2 - u_1(t), u_3(t)$	5.3923×10^5	3.2784×10^4	0.0608
$S_4 - u_1(t), u_2(t), u_3(t)$	5.3924×10^5	3.2719×10^4	-6.5000

From Table 5, we see that the ICER for S_2 is higher when compared with that of S_4 . At this juncture, we exclude S_2 and are left with S_4 . Therefore, the most cost-effective strategy among the four strategies analyzed in this work is the combination of all three optimal control interventions (S_4).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Strategy 4, which combines all three optimal controls, is the most cost-effective strategy that can be implemented to mitigate the community spread of TF. Coincidentally, the strategy is also identified as the most efficient among the four strategies analyzed in this paper, as it averts the highest number of TF cases in the population. It is therefore recommended that the government, policy makers, health workers, researchers, and individuals should consider vaccination of susceptible individuals where available, as well as adequate treatment of symptomatic infectious humans and proper environmental sanitation with good personal hygiene, be encouraged to avert the alarming spread of the disease, and where possible, totally eradicate TF.

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